

IN-VITRO ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTY DETERMINATION OF THE PLANT EXTRACTS *LASIA SPINOSA* (LIN.) FAMILY ARACEAE

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Abstract: Analysis of the free radical scavenging activities of the selected *Lasia spino* methanol extracts revealed a concentration dependent free radical scavenging activity resulting from reduction of DPPH, Nitric Oxide, Hydroxyl radical and superoxide radical radical to non-radical form. The scavenging activity of Ascorbic acid, a known antioxidant used as positive control, was however higher. DPPH radical is considered to be a model for a lipophilic radical. A chain in lipophilic radicals was initiated by the lipid autoxidation. DPPH is a stable free radical at room temperature and accepts an electron or hydrogen radical to become a stable diamagnetic molecule. The reduction capacity of DPPH was determined by the decrease in its absorbance at 517 nm, which is induced by antioxidant. Positive DPPH test suggests that the samples were free radical scavengers. The scavenging effect of l-Ascorbic acid, and plant extracts increased gradually with increase in concentration. Nitric oxide plays an important role in various types of inflammatory processes in the body.

Keywords: *Lasia spino*, DPPH, Nitric oxide, l-Ascorbic acid,

Introduction: Free radicals can be defined as atoms or molecules or molecular fragments containing one or more unpaired electrons in their atomic or molecular orbitals. The free radical formation in the body is a continuous and unavoidable process of human body [1]. The immune system, metabolic processes, stress, dietary factors, environmental factors, toxins and some drugs are responsible for generation of free radicals [2]. Each and every cell present in the body produces free radicals hence is prone to free radical attack. Biological

compounds available in human changes their property after free radical attack which may alter cellular function of human body and even leads to death of cells or tissue which responsible for generating various diseases. The most susceptible biological compounds are lipid, protein, DNA etc. [3-4]. Free radicals play important role in phagocytosis, apoptosis, detoxification reactions as mediator and executioner of precancerous and infectious cells. It maintains cellular homeostasis in body by participating in various signaling pathways. Free radical control many metabolic and cellular processes including, oxygen sensing, proliferation, vascular contraction, wound healing, muscles contraction, gene expression, regulation of transcription, and signal transduction. It also involve in generation of biochemical reactions which are responsible for production of prostaglandins, hydroxylation of proline and lysine, oxidation of xanthine [5-6]. Anti-oxidant are the substances that significantly delays or inhibits oxidation of that substrate, when present at low concentrations compared with that of an oxidizable substrate [7]. Human body produces large number of free radical which have role in pathogenesis of various disease hence body maintain redox balance by producing various anti-oxidant which can broadly divided in two groups i.e. enzymatic antioxidants and non-enzymatic anti-oxidants [8]. The enzymatic antioxidants are divided into primary and secondary enzymatic antioxidants. The primary enzymatic antioxidants such as glutathione peroxidase, catalase and superoxide dismutase prevent the formation of free radical by neutralizing them [9]. A large number of medicinal plants and their purified constituents have shown antioxidant activity.

Material and Methods:

Plant: Plant rhizome was first defatted with petroleum ether and then treated with methanol and the methanolic extract was examined for in vitro antioxidant activity

Reagents: Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), Naphtyl Ethylene Diamine Dihydrochloride (NEDD), Nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT). Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide reduced (NADH), Thiobarbituric acid, Phenazine methosulphate.

Preliminary Phytoprofiles screening of *Lasia spinosa*: *Lasia spinosa* powdered (100 g) was successively extracted with the following solvents of increasing polarity in a soxhlet apparatus. The dried powder was packed in Soxhlet apparatus extracted with 250 ml of methanol extracts. The total yield of the extracts obtained after removing the solvents was calculated. All the extracts were concentrated by distilling the solvents and the extracts were dried in an oven. Each time before extracting with the next solvent, the marc was

dried in an air. The consistency, color, appearance of the extracts and their percentage yield were noted.

in vitro antioxidant property

DPPH scavenging activity: Assay method is based on the reduction of methanolic solution of DPPH by free radical scavenger. The process was done by taking 0.2ml aliquot of the different concentration of extract and standards were added to 4 ml of DPPH in methanol solution (100 μ M). After incubation at 30°C for 20 minute the absorbance of each solution was determined at 490nm against a suitable blank. A control test was performed without the extract or standards. Percentage scavenging and IC50 value (IC50 value is the concentration of the sample required to inhibit 50% of the radical) were calculated.

Hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity: As the H₂O₂ concentration is decreased by scavenger compounds, the absorbance value at 230 nm is also decreased. Various concentration of extract, the compound and standard in methanol (1ml) were added to 2ml of H₂O, in phosphate buffer saline. After 10 minute the absorbance was measured at 230nm against a blank solution containing the extract or standard but without the reagent control test was performed without the extract or standards. Percentage scavenging and IC 50 values (IC50) value is the concentration of the sample required to inhibit 50% of radical) were calculated

Nitric oxide scavenging activity: Nitric oxide, because of its unpaired electron, is classified as a free radical and displays important reaction with certain type of proteins and other free radicals. This method is based on the inhibition of nitric oxide radical generated from sodium nitroprusside in buffer saline and measured by 0.33% sulphanillic acid solution in 20% glacial acetic acid and 0.1% naphthyl ethylene diamine dihydrochloride (NEDD). The reaction mixture (6 ml) containing sodium nitroprusside (10mM, 4 ml) phosphate buffered saline (1ml) and the extract and standard solution (1ml) were incubated at 25°C for 150 minute. After incubation 0.5ml of the reaction mixture was removed and 1ml of the sulfanilic acid reagent (0.33% in 20% glacial acetic acid) was mixed and allowed to stand for 5 minute for completion of diazotization reaction and then 1ml of NEDD was added. Mixed and allowed to stand for another 30 minute in diffused light. The absorbance was measured at 540nm against the corresponding blank solution

Super oxide anion scavenging activity: The super oxide radical reduces nitroblue tetrazolium to a blue color formazone that can be measured at 560nm. Measurement of superoxide anion scavenging activity of methanolic plant extract was carried based on the method described by Nishikimi with slight modification. One ml of Nitroblue tetrazolium solution (156 μ M NBT in 100 mM Phosphate buffer, pH 7.4), 1ml NADH solution (468 μ M solution in 100mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) and 1 ml of sample solution of plant extract in water were mixed. The reaction was started by addition of 1ml of Phenazine methosulphate (PMS) solution (60 μ M PMS in 100 mM Phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) to the mixture. The reaction mixture was incubated at 25°C for 5 minute and the absorbance at 560 nm was measured against blank samples. Decreased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicated increased superoxide anion scavenging activity all data are an average of triplicate analyses

Results and discussion

Physicochemical parameter studies on selected plants: Total ash of *Lasia spino* was found 6.4%. Water soluble ash was found 2.91 % whereas 0.91% was acid insoluble ash. The ethanol soluble extractive values were found to be 9.6% and water-soluble extractive values were found to be 13.8 %. The moisture content of the powder estimated as percentage loss on drying (LOD) was found to be 29.2 % w/w. Total ash of *Lasia spino* was found 5.7%. Water soluble ash was found 2.68 % whereas 0.98% was acid insoluble ash. The ethanol soluble extractive values were found to be 8.3 % and water-soluble extractive values were found to be 10.9% and loss on drying (LOD) was found to be 27.86% w/w.

Extraction of the Drugs: The coarse powder of the fruit of *Lasia spino* was subjected to successive solvent extraction using solvents of ascending polarity. After extraction the percentage yield of each extract was calculated with reference to the air-dried drug used for the study. The percentage yield and other characteristic features of the extracts are tabulated below.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening: The qualitative phytochemical screening of the tubers for the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrate, reducing sugars, glycosides like anthraquinones, flavanoids, saponins, tannins, phenolic compounds, fixed oils, fats, proteins, amino acids and sterols in petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts of the rhizome of *Lasia spino* were carried out.

Analysis of the free radical scavenging activities of the selected *Lasia spino* methanolic extracts revealed a concentration dependent free radical scavenging activity resulting from reduction of DPPH, NO, Hydroxyl radical and superoxide radical radical to non-radical form. The scavenging activity of Ascorbic acid, a known antioxidant used as positive control, was however higher. DPPH radical is considered to be a model for a lipophilic radical. The scavenging effect of l-Ascorbic acid, and plant extracts increased gradually with increase in concentration.

Nitric oxide plays an important role in various types of inflammatory processes in the body. In the present study the rhizome extracts of selected *Lasia spino* checked for its inhibitory effect on Nitric oxide production. Results revealed that all the tested extracts showed the percentage of inhibition in a dose dependent manner. The methanol extract of *Lasia spino* at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of nitric oxide radical scavenging activity compared to other extract. The methanol extract of *Lasia spino* at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of nitric oxide radical scavenging activity.

The hydroxyl radical is an extremely reactive free radical formed in biological systems and has been implicated as a highly damaging species in free radical pathology, capable of damaging almost every molecule found in living cells. The effect of the selected plant extracts was assessed by means of the iron (II)- dependent DNA damage assay. All the results showed hydroxyl radical scavenging activity in a dose dependent manner.

The methanol extract of *Lasia spino* at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extract. The ethanol extract of *Lasia spino* at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity.

Superoxide is a reactive oxygen species, which can cause damage to the cells and DNA leading to various diseases. The ethanol extract of *Lasia spino* at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of superoxide radical activity scavenging. The ethanol extract of *Lasia spino* at varied concentrations showed remarkable inhibitory effect of superoxide radical scavenging activity.

Summary And Conclusion: Studies were undertaken to characterization in vitro antioxidant activity evaluation of the methanolic extracts of rhizome of *Lasia spinosa*. The crude drug was subjected to leaf constant, ash value and extractive value

determination. Significant antioxidant activity has been found in the methanolic extract when in vitro antioxidant property determination was performed.

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Table 1: Organoleptic and Physicochemical parameters of *Lasia spino*

S. No.	Parameters	Cucurbita pepo
1	Shape and size	Fruits are ovoid ribbed size 13-45cm long covered with hard peel
2	Colour	outer (greenish yellow), inner (yellow)
3	Odour	Characteristics
4	Taste	Sweet
5	Total ash	6.4 % w/w
6	Water soluble ash	2.91 % w/w
7	Acid insoluble ash	0.91 % w/w
8	Foreign organic matter determination	1.05 % w/w
9	Ethanol soluble extractive	9.6 % w/w
10	Water-soluble extractive	13.8 % w/w
11	Loss on drying (%)	29.2 % w/w

Table 2: Phytochemical analysis parameters of *Lasia spino*

Tests of Phytoconstituents	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i> fruit extracts
Extractive value	6.5
1. Alkaloids	
a) Mayer's reagent	-
b) Dragendorff's reagent	-
2. Flavonoids	
a) Shinoda test	-
3. Saponins	
a) Froth test	-
4. Carbohydrate	
a) Molisch's test	-
c) Test for gums	-
d) Test for mucilage	-
5. Phytosterols	
a) Libermann-Burchard test	+
c) Salkowski reaction:	+
6. Tannins and Phenolic	
a) With Lead acetate	-
7. Cardiac glycoside	
a) (a) Borntrager's test	-
b) Legal's test	-
8. Coumarins	
a) With ammonia	-
b) Hydroxylamine HCl	-

9. Proteins	
a) Biuret test	-
10. Triterpens	
a) Vanillin sulphuric acid	+

Table 3: *Lasia spino* extract on DPPH radical scavenging

Concentration	100µg/ml	200 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	400 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	74.12	77.14	82.14	85.41	96.14
MELS	62.47	71.14	75.87	78.14	82.59

Table 4: *Lasia spino* extract on Nitric oxide radical scavenging

Concentration	100µg/ml	200 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	400 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	76.24	80.14	84.98	90.25	97.54
MELS	58.47	65.14	69.18	72.58	78.94

Table 5: *Lasia spino* extract on Hydroxyl radical scavenging

Concentration	100µg/ml	200 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	400 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	60.25	65.47	70.28	75.15	91.36
MELS	50.27	57.15	61.84	65.63	71.24

Table 6: *Lasia spino* extract on Super oxide radical scavenging activity

Concentration	100µg/ml	200 µg/ml	300 µg/ml	400 µg/ml	500 µg/ml
Ascorbic acid	35.25	45.35	54.17	62.87	70.84
MELS	31.87	34.98	47.54	60.45	62.87

Table 7: *In vitro* 50% inhibition concentration (IC₅₀) of *Lasia spino* extract on various models

Extract /compound	50% inhibition concentration (IC ₅₀)			
	DPPH model (µg/ml)	NO model (µg/ml)	Hydroxyl radical model (µg/ml)	superoxide model (µg/ml)
Ascorbic acid	66	67	82	160
MELS	85.64	88	107	399

Figure 1: Graphical representation of *Lasia spino* extract on DPPH model

Figure 2: Graphical representation of *Lasia spino* extract on Nitric oxide radical scavenging model

Figure 3: Graphical representation of *Lasia spino* extract on Hydroxyl radical scavenging model

Figure 4: Graphical representation of *Lasia spino extract* on Super oxide radical scavenging model

Figure 5: Graphical representation of 50% Inhibitory Concentration (IC₅₀) of *Lasia spino extract* and Ascorbic acid on various models